

The Potential Socio-Economic Impacts of a North Korean Invasion of South Korea

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Abstract

In the event of an invasion of South Korea by North Korea, we could see many tech companies that rely on manufacturers such as Samsung, LX Semicon, or LG, take significant hits in their pipeline and potential output. This creates a worrying paradigm with the impacts of an invasion being unquantifiable due to the global reliance on South Korean companies. Over 20% of the global semiconductor market is produced in South Korea, and since semiconductors are among the most valuable man-made components, this would cause inflation to increase sharply and unforeseen consequences to occur. In this paper, I will highlight the potential consequences of an invasion, the evidence for said consequences, and will reiterate why we shouldn't display overreliance on *any* country, no matter if they are an ally or not, and should strive to diversify who we rely on.

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Apple, the company worth over a trillion dollars, references South Korean companies 33 times inside its officially published Supply Chain report. One of the said companies is SK Hynix. SK Hynix is a global powerhouse in the industry of semiconductor manufacturing, and more specifically, the NAND flash and DRAM market. SK Hynix accounts for over 20% of the global semiconductor market in total, 51% of the global NAND Flash market, and 73% of the global DRAM market. This may seem like a trivial problem, assuming, of course, they are located in safe, not unstable territories. However, that is the exact issue with SK Hynix; being headquartered in South Korea, only has one other base of operations, located in mainland China, which, as of late, is another country with which our relations are unstable. Another big player in Apple's supply chain, and many other companies' supply chains, is Samsung SDI, the

manufacturer of most of Apple's batteries inside its products. SDI also has a manufacturing plant inside Mainland China, but as previously stated, that would be a lost cause if such a war were to re-enter its active status. Another member of the Samsung group that manufactures for Apple is Samsung Electro-Mechanics Company Limited, a huge division of Samsung, that manufactures many of its semiconductor substrates and processes. Unlike the previous companies, SEMC is a publicly traded company, of which Samsung only owns 23.7% of, making Samsung the controlling stakeholder, but not the majority owner. SEMC is located in South Korea, with major operations also in Thailand and the Philippines. This means that SEMC has a fallback plan in the event of an invasion. Additionally, new industry rumors have reported that Apple is shifting to SEMC as its manufacturer for the majority of iPhone, iPad, and other Apple products' camera sensors, which were previously mainly manufactured by Sony. These are just two of the major players in the South Korean segment of the global Apple supply chain, and an even smaller segment of the global tech supply chain. For better or for worse, all of the companies I have just cited have at least one segment/base of operations inside the Chinese mainland. However, there are a few companies like LX Semicon, which is the main supplier that makes the mixed signal semiconductors used inside Apple OLED Display Driver Integrated circuits. Although in the event of a war, theoretically, LX Semicon could shift its DDI production to Japan or the U.S., as it has subsidiaries in both, it would be economically disastrous for Apple and many other companies. Though Apple does have other partners in the OLED DDI manufacturing space. Apple has only been said to recently been moving to using LX Semicon more compared to Samsung System LSI, which they have used in their iPhones since the introduction of OLED screens on iPhones in 2017 with the iPhone X. In addition, the other major display manufacturer

besides Samsung, particularly for Apple's OLED iPad models¹, is LG, another South Korean conglomerate. LG also provides the display tech for Apple's standalone Apple Studio Display, the cheaper offering compared to the Pro Display XDR.² This means that not just Apple's displays, which are already provided by Samsung and LG, but also Apple's OLED DDI's provided by LX Semicon would be completely landlocked from production. This is incredibly alarming, considering the socioeconomic status of the world as of late. These trends also continue to prove evident when you take a look at the major medical manufacturers, of which Samsung is one of them, the rare earth metal industry, or any of the technological manufacturing processes. We can also use Samsung itself as a case study, with Samsung trailing behind Apple in market share, but still holding a 20% market share, according to Counterpoint Research, and if a North Korean invasion of South Korea were to occur, users all across the globe could be severely affected in their work and personal lives. Additionally, the capital of South Korea, Seoul, is only 31 miles from the DMZ, where the two countries' armies meet. Combined, all of this evidence results in a worrying paradigm, and a cautionary tale about overreliance on any country, regardless of origin.

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¹ Apple has not explicitly stated that they have partnered with LG for the 2024 iPad Pro, but it is widely confirmed by experts from teardowns of the product

² *Apple has not explicitly stated that they have partnered with LG for the Apple Studio Display, but it is widely confirmed from teardowns of the product*

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³ Apple, as previously stated with other footnotes, doesn't publicly state directly what products come from who, but the rumour has proven to be credible.